
PRAGMATIC FEATURES OF THE POETRY TEXT

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Abstract: This article discusses the pragmatic features, history, uniqueness and some aspects of the poetry text.

Key words: poetic speech, pragmatics, lexeme, communicative intention, pragmatic field.

INTRODUCTION

In linguistics, the inability of the field of semantics to adequately explain the socio-linguistic and other non-linguistic components of oral speech led to the emergence of pragmatics. "Pragmatics" is derived from the Greek word *pragma*, which means "work", "action".

LITERATURE REVIEW

The first stages of the formation of the science of pragmatics are based on the philosophical concepts of scientists such as Ch. Peirce, W. James, D. Dewey, and Ch. Morris of the late 19th and early 20th centuries. At first, the concept of pragmatics began to be used in semiotic scientific research dedicated to the study of the structure of the linguistic situation (as the relationship between the speaker and the listener) in a dynamic procedural aspect.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

Some linguists consider pragmatics to be a science that studies relationships in the text, while others recognize that it is a method of using linguistic tools to achieve the desired goal. In any case, pragmatics is seen as inextricably linked with the speech process and is a new field of research that works in harmony with sociolinguistics and semantics.

Although a number of research works on theoretical pragmatics, pragmalinguistics, text pragmatics, and translation pragmatics have been carried out in today's linguistics, in Uzbek linguistics the pragmatics of poetic speech and the structural features of language units expressing it have not been sufficiently studied. Poetry and pragmatics, at first glance, seem to be fundamentally different concepts.

Pragmatics is dominated by expediency, result orientation, and the advantage of action, while high creativity, emotion, broad outlook, and artistic expression prevail in poetry. Various actions, which are the main direction of pragmatics, i.e. questions, messages, promises, gratitude, advice, requests and other communication processes are manifested in poetic speech under the artistic expression of the author. The pragmatic potential of the poetic text requires the author's use of linguistic means as a pragmatic influence of the language in an appropriate and targeted manner.

It is known that the communicative goal of the author (the transmitter of information) in the poetic text is one of the main characteristics of the communication process, and such a goal is linguistically realized in the structure and content of the poetic text as a purposefully created communicative intention. Another feature of such a communicative purpose is reflected in its dependence on the content and structural structure of the text, and its communicative effect on the receiver.

In a poetic speech, the mental state of the speaker, his attitude towards the given information, exerts its influence on the listener and expresses the intention to encourage him to a certain action. In any poetic text, the author's personal emotional attitude, inner feelings, mental state, and main goal can be understood directly from the content of the words expressed in the verses of the poem. Accordingly, the following types of poetic text pragmatics are distinguished:

- constative (when expressing the content of a message, definition, confirmation, notification);
- predicative (assumption, when the content of the prediction is expressed);
- directive (when expressing content such as command, request, question, persecution);
- commission (promise, offer);
- Acknowledgment (congratulations, takalluf, respect, etc.).

Researching the pragmatic features of the poetic text, determining the communicative nature of the linguistic units in the original language, in this case the influence of the communication situation occurring in the process of expressing the character of the lyrical character, communicative intention, pragmatic purpose, thereby the pragmatic content of the artistic work through linguistic and non-linguistic means. provides an opportunity to determine the methods and means of expression. In this case, the "lexical" meaning of the word serves to determine the content of the expression, while the contextual meaning indicates the intentionality of the symbol represented by the material, that is, it is directed to a certain goal, related to a concrete object. Consequently, the semantic-syntactic construction of the thought generally reflects the pragmatic experience of the author, which includes cognitive knowledge and communicative goals.

In the poetic text, the author's skill in using words is in the first place. This expresses the interaction between the pragmatics of poetic speech and the field of lexicology of linguistics.

The components of the lexeme sememe are considered a reserve of linguistic pragmatics with neutral, stylistic coloration and the presence or absence of emotional signs (emotional semantics specific to the lexeme sememe) depending on their function in speech [2.41]. In the poetic text, the author uses lexemes with stylistic color to express his inner goal in the speech. The pragmatic features of lexical units are present in the lexical structure, and their positive or negative coloring serves to form a pragmatic meaning. In a poetic text, the meaning of the lexeme changes according to the author's intention and the context, and the meaning comes to the fore. The meaning fulfills the communicative purpose of the speaker.

Buni M.Yusufning “Qora quyosh” dostonidan keltirilgan parchada ko‘rishimiz mumkin:

Menga juda aziz
Uning siymosi,
Bir qaragam,
Yo‘qdek sira qiyosi.
U bir bag‘ridaryo,
Bir bag‘ritoshdir,
U bir quyosh
Ammo -
Qora quyoshdir!

The poet "It is the black sun!" in the verse, the lyrical hero is compared to the sun, but in nature, the sun is yellow, not black, and it radiates equal light to the world. It gives life to all living beings by giving heat power. Why did the poet describe the Sun as "black" and not "yellow" in the epic? - the question arises.

Linguists H. Ne'matov and R. Rasulov divide the components of the semema into naming, expression and task semes. Among these schemas, the schema of expression is the object of research for pragmatics. They say that atash semas name objects, items, signs, properties, quantities, etc. in the objective world and determine the connection of semas with the concepts in a person's memory. As the word changes the place of its functional use in the context, the meaning of the expression describing the concrete attitude of the speaker takes the first place in the place of the term, as a result, the need for pragmatic analysis is felt [4.40].

The poet described the Sun in "black" color, not "yellow", and placed the negative aspects of the character of the lyrical hero in the root of the word "black". By giving the description of the lyrical hero under such lines, the poet informs about the events of the time of the Soviets, and the listener understands the author's attitude to reality

and makes a conclusion. When the receiver receives the transmitted information, he enters into a specific attitude towards the information expressed in the poetic text. As a result, the communicative goal of the author (the communicator) is summarized in the pragmatic field with the private relations of the recipient of the information.

Under the concept of pragmatic field, it is assumed that language and speech units form a mutually certain system from the point of view of the function of expressing the attitude of the author of the text to the objective existence, as well as to the thought he expresses [2.140]. The author's pragmatic potential takes the lead in this.

Pragmatic potential is the fact that the information in the text has a pragmatic effect on the listener, that is, the information reflected in the poetic text affects the listener's feelings and evokes a certain emotional reaction. Revealing the semantic meaning contained in the whole composition of the poetic text, the correct choice of specific language resources in the implementation of artistic communication, and the appropriate use of symbols in solving artistic and aesthetic problems are required. Because the symbolic meaning of the poetic work is the main field of manifestation of the author's originality and shows that the author himself is the creator of the artistic reality.

CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

In conclusion, it can be said that in a poetic text, the poet's transmission of information important to the recipient, conveying it to the recipient is manifested in linguistic units, and the way the recipient receives the information and his attitude towards it creates poetic pragmatics. . In poetic pragmatics, there is a system of actions for the formation and understanding of speech, in which information is exchanged between the author and the reader.

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